

Critical Analysis of Crime and Vulnerability in Karachi: Socio-Economic Determinants and Solutions through Public Art and Urban Environmental Design

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Abstract

Karachi is a metropolitan city and has many complicated issues like crime and security challenges. The public art is a medium, which transforms the social harmony and draws new theories of social harmony and social design. The potential of public art interventions, such as murals, sculptures, and community installations, to reclaim dangerous areas, promote civic pride, and promote shared ownership of the urban environment is assessed. Simultaneously, principles of Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED) are considered to assess how spatial planning, visibility, and accessibility can reduce opportunities for criminal activity. Using qualitative research method through content analysis, the investigators have attempted to justify the research and have highlighted the outcomes of the study. The finding of this study highlights that the condition of cities across the globe can be improved through public art, because it helps to reduce crime rate. It is observed that promoting art and culture through public art graffiti and monument creates a healthy impact on people and environment which as a result eliminates chaos that penetrates within the society. This study explores the social, cultural, and political meanings of the unique visual work and it argues that the positive aspects of public art and the perception of security through creating and placing designs and statues in the city. This concept has already been adopted by western countries, to set the example of crime reduction through public art to a great extent. The proven factors of this research emphasizes that public art contributes in the elimination of crime throughout the city. However, wall chalk continues and is expanding as a new form of communication. Various methods of chalking have been found on the wall, including popular messages, commercials, and some works of art. Art work and graffiti is generally seen as a reflection of cultural aspiration of the society.

Keywords: Public Art, City Environmental Design, Graffiti, Urban Structures, Urban Planning.

Introduction

Art is normally displayed in galleries and buildings to show exclusivity. But nowadays art work is displayed in outdoor and public places for people to enjoy and perceive different messages; this sort of art is called public art. Most of the time public art involves the public and is used to express feelings ideas and thoughts to deliver a message to the public (Grodach, 2009). Public art is occasionally viewed as a representation of political and cultural goals that converge with the attractiveness of the city, according to Mustafa (2009), and historic cities can be revitalized with the aid of public art. The ill planned and filthy areas of old towns will be changed into colourful, alive spaces by strategically placing site-specific public art at street corners, back alleyways, and wall spaces (Lefebvre, 2017). Public art influences the city's physical and visual qualities as well as its social and economic climate. Urban areas with public art will see an improvement in their visual quality. Murals or other three-dimensional public art can breathe fresh life into a drab wall. Public artwork influences the city's physical and visual quality as well as its social and economic climate. Urban areas with public art will see an improvement in their visual quality. When public art becomes a part of people's everyday life, it improves their quality of life both viscerally and experientially due to regular interaction and having its impact them psychologically as well (Shin Dongshuk, 1999). Shin further added that public art is supposed to improve people's quality of life when they interact with it on a regular basis. By virtue of public art, an abandoned alleyway that was formerly full of mould and trash can be cleaned up. Public artwork impacts effectively when the communities are well-maintained before and after its completion. As a result, rather of appearing

gloomy and unwelcoming, the external structure of historic buildings in the city can be improved, especially in a city as old as Ipoh that is subject to weather-related ageing. This is crucial to create a welcoming atmosphere for both locals and tourists to have a better view of the city. The inclusion of public art in the vicinity of heritage buildings encourages the adaptive reuse of those structures. Due to the large percentage of abandoned buildings in older cities, public art is placed in close proximity to these structures Dickson (2008), to draw in visitors and encourage the conversion of further buildings into cafes, restaurants, galleries, boutiques, and hotels, for instance in Lahore, Islamabad and Karachi old areas are converted into decorated food streets. More people get engaged in outdoor activities, when there are more visual sights of public art, which will open up additional possibilities for the nearby buildings to be put to new uses. Increased activity related to public art viewing will draw more people to the outdoor spaces, creating more opportunities for the neighbouring buildings to be used for new purposes. Initially, the movement surrounding the open expressions will support the buildings' adaptable re-use; later, the modified re-used buildings will support the activity surrounding the open expressions. This cycle continues to create a beneficial interaction between outdoor areas, open expressions, and historic legacy structures.

In order to ensure a satisfactory level of stylistic quality, it is essential to preserve the legacy of buildings by restoring their facades and maintaining their structural integrity with the support of local experts. Additionally, this response is triggered by the open expressions, which reduces the need for undiscovered, unused land for progress (Greenfield advancement) and instead focuses more on repurposing existing buildings or choosing infill improvements that make them more manageable. Open communication fosters greater progress for both locals and tourists. An illustration of the graffiti in the cities shows how the areas surrounding the open expressions create contemporary, lively spaces within the historic city, while the open expressions themselves remain underutilized centers. Apart from that, the city will have a stronger sense of identity and be well-known due to the unrestricted expressions available across the city. The city's open expressions and overall attractive appearance would allow people to sense its proximity. As previously stated, an old city's aesthetic or physical modifications will draw more people's attention and higher numbers of people typically result in more social engagements within the city (Ferrell, 1996).

Karachi's high crime rates are deeply tied to the city's painful economic and social divisions. Many struggle without work, while the city expands at a dizzying pace. At the same time, basics like water, electricity, and schooling are out of reach for too many, creating fertile ground for crime (Gayer, 2014). In poorer neighborhoods, the lack of proper roads, safe parks, or places to gather weakens the community's fabric, leaving streets feeling abandoned and unseen. This profound deprivation fosters a sense of being shut out, which, as scholars point out, allows shadow economies and criminal networks to grow (Gayer, 2014). The inequality in access to housing, education, and transport deepens the city's divides, trapping some in a cycle where they are more likely to suffer from crime and be pulled into it (Hasan & Mohib, 2003). But hope can be found in reshaping the city's own streets and spaces. Thoughtful public art and intentional urban design can be powerful, grassroots solutions. By creating vibrant and inviting public areas, we can encourage small businesses, bring more life outdoors, and naturally deter crime—an approach known as Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (Cozens & Love, 2015). When communities themselves lead art projects in neglected corners of the city, it builds local pride and connection. This offers young people positive outlets and pushes back against the stigma of being marginalized. In the end, making Karachi safer for all means tackling poverty and redesigning the urban environment together, as two parts of the same crucial effort. In the heart of Karachi, a city of relentless energy and profound contrasts, the rhythm of daily life is too often pierced by the staccato beat of crime. For its millions of residents, vulnerability is not an abstract concept but

a texture of their urban experience—a shadow in an unlit alley, a tension on a crowded bus, the silent worry for a child’s walk home. While law enforcement is the immediate response, the roots of this insecurity dig deep into the city’s very soil, intertwined with stark socio-economic inequalities, fractured public spaces, and a pervasive sense of civic disconnection. This article moves beyond conventional analysis to explore a more human-centric vision of safety. It argues that Karachi’s resilience lies not only in policing but in healing its urban fabric. We examine how chronic issues like unemployment, inadequate housing, and social exclusion fuel cycles of vulnerability. Crucially, we propose that solutions can be woven into the city’s landscape itself. Can a vibrant mural transform a neglected wall from a blind spot into a point of community pride? Can thoughtful lighting and inclusive park design turn a barren lot into a well-used playground, naturally watched over by residents? This is a critical exploration of how public art and empathetic environmental design can be powerful, often overlooked, tools. They offer a path to reclaim spaces, rebuild a shared sense of belonging, and craft a Karachi where safety grows organically from the ground up.

Theoretical Background

Common source and motivation for road craftsmanship culture are found in a few key areas across the world. In East Europe, most post-communist nations have a vibrant road craftsmanship culture, and in North Norway, Stavanger hosts the annual Nuart Festival, one of the leading events in Europe for promoting street art. In West Britain, London is one of the world’s most pro-graffiti cities, and at the same time it is one of the cities that officially prohibits and severely punishes road craftsmanship (Niccolai, 2001). Bristol, largely because of Banksy, is also part of a thriving street art scene. Across the ocean, in North America USA, New York City is home to street art, and in South America Brazil, São Paulo is another capital of street art (Austin, 2001). While in Australia one of the most vibrant and diverse cultures of street art in the world can be found in Melbourne, Asia has not yet caught up with the trend. The Middle East, on the other hand, is slowly catching up: Iranian artist A1one has been featured in Tokyo-based design magazine PingMag for his works on Tehran walls (Uleshka 2007), the Israeli West Bank barrier has become a location for street art, in the same way as the Berlin Wall; Turkey has a growing number of local artists, and a great number of foreign artists display their work as well in Istanbul. According to Tunc Dindas, The street’s art work that can be observed particularly in Istanbul is increasing day by day. Which attracts tourists, and yet it makes possible to see the work of many Turkish and foreign artists in the Taksim area (Dindas 2009).

The social disorganization will handle on the talk about with respect to the way in which the road craftsmanship (spray painting) is undermining specialist and the social control framework, as well as impacting the culture (rising from subculture to counter culture). With respect to the anomie it is found that this sort of development damages or not the norms and desires of the society. The researchers aim to address the question: to what extent is street art a deviant practice that transforms the “authentically alien” spaces? In the event that we consider retreatism, it represents the third form of deviant social adjustment (Merton, 1957). From an aesthetical viewpoint the art work with respect to craftsmanship as a chosen or open framework, the questions concern the independence of the aesthetic work of craftsmanship and the non-referential dialect, what are the new propensities in street craftsmanship and what are the possible contrasts in road craftsmanship within the West and within the East? With respect to the interactivity, the researchers allude to the changes that occur in our “microwave community” with the plausibility to connect between road specialists and eradicate their mysterious status. Moreover alluding to the unused patterns in road craftsmanship that are utilizing modern techniques (e.g. spray painting 3D).

Research Objectives

1. To find out the importance of art in controlling the crime rate in Karachi.
2. To know about the cultural reflections of art and graffiti in promoting peace.
3. To understand how art can change the environmental conditions of society and reduce negativity.

Significance of Study

In many cities, there are small, often overlooked spots—quiet corners where few people pass by, gradually losing their connection to the surrounding community. However, when residents bring creativity into these spaces, the results can be surprisingly powerful. Wall chalking and graffiti is a very strong medium of sloganeering and to advertise, promote and establish serene environment through art work, particularly in context of Karachi city. In Karachi we can view political text on walls, promoting the political party's ideology. Art work on walls portrays our mindset and cultural belongings as well and it adds emotional attachment and on the other hand it builds relationship among people in public and private space (Hall, 2018). It is also a medium of expression and communication or we can say that opinions are made and spread through wall chalking. Demographically we know that Karachi is divided into six districts and this city is an economic hub of Pakistan and it contributes major portion of revenue for the entire country (World Bank, 2018). This study holds great significance as it digs deep into the thoughtful design of city through art work and explores that crime can be reduces and peace and safety can be improved addressing crime though prism of art work and making vulnerable areas of Karachi into vibrant and lively spaces Cysek-Pawlak, Serafin & Polishchuk (2025), for example, food streets (**Burns Road, Hussainabad Food Street, Do Darya, and the DHA Food Streets**) and many roadside graffiti in Karachi. Such vibrant urban environments provide innovative strategies to reduce crime and promoting safety (Karachi Police Department, 2022). Above all it impacts people's psyche and improves behaviours and promotes peace and harmony in the society, thereby improving quality of life for all (Felbab-Brown, 2019).

Limitations of Research

Public art is not a onetime process; it continuously requires maintenance, participation of the community and support at municipal level, but unfortunately long-term sustenance is not empirically assessed. Therefore we cannot say anything definitely about the impact over time, maybe timely it creates an impact, but its long-term impact cannot be promised. There is a chance that content analysis method might influence the understanding in terms of cultural and security significance and might reflect researcher's standpoint as qualitative research is interpretive in nature (De Haan, 1990). The CPTED principles are discussed conceptually and the reduction in crime rate cannot be exactly evaluated as we cannot determine the crime levels shaped by several factors like poverty, lack of education, lack of civic sense, poor governance, urbanization and other socio-economic factors (Pakistan Institute of Criminology, 2020). This study has focused on examining environmental factors and its solutions, but further studies are needed to find out urban variables which trigger criminal activities.

Literature Review

Wall chalking, graffiti and advertisement on walls through any contemporary city is kind of walkthrough of their culture and it reflects the aura of that city, which is also represented by hand drawn figures, murals, markings etc. and it carries the emotional pulse of the city in raw form. Whatever is written or painted on walls is not any disorder, but a vibrant layer of people's subconscious and clear projection of people's heart shared in public space. Such writings and art work serves as a tool for communicating in a collective manner. Researchers such as Castellón (1978), Cohan (1975), and Freeman (1966) claimed that such acts are deliberate actions to share cultural sentiments and it is a form of social identity in physical space. People actually use wall graffiti as formal platforms to articulate their aspirations and concerns. Such markings evolve without any support or permanence of institutions at public and private level. But sometimes public and private domain also use them to disseminate knowledge or awareness on social matters or sometimes just for the beautification of the city (Mahmood, Saleem, & Baig, 2005). Public art has gained attention of many scholars and many theories are developed by urban theorists. Simone and Pieterse (2017) argued that wall chalking and decorated walls actually deliver texture of urban life and it is a visual interpretation is true forms of

communication. According to them it is very challenging to understand the unexplained context. Whereas, Dovey (2012) said, these informal practices can be seen in all cities in urban centers and even in remote areas. They are kind of flyers, micro expressions which carry deep social structures, power dynamics, and cultural rhythms. Wekker contributed that serious attention should be given to these informal expressions to dig deep into the social cohesion to understand the complexity of everyday life, because we begin to understand multilayered myths and stories told by cite walls (Wekker, 2017).

People from different social sectors like community organizers, anthropologists, policy makers and urban sociologists thinks that marks on walls are not just for decorative purpose, but they are powerful indicators and is kind of medium that tells stories out of graffiti (National Institute of Urban Infrastructure Planning, 2019). The indicators like shared sense of belonging trust and willingness for mutual participation opens a window of spontaneous public expressions, which lead to a unique understanding. According to Hansen and Verkaaik (2009) decorated walls function like open forums where people show their emotions, depressions, disputes, and desires directly. Whereas Ahmed (2020) argued that walls are also used to broadcast messages by different groups like religious people, advertisers, political parties and local associations etc., he further added that it is a way of communicating informally and without using any kind of media forum messages are conveyed. Wall chalking and wall painting is practiced even in communities/cities where it is restricted by law. People view them differently; some approves it, whereas some consider it as a display of deeper cultural, social expectations Menor (2015), some view it as a local art peace, where some consider it as distraction. Broken-window theory was first introduced by Wilson and Kelling (1982), and later on Menor also discussed this theory indicates disorder, because many graffiti are unethical or immoral which can lead to criminal activities or immoral activities (Menor, 2015). In the context of this theory we can say that unaddressed graffiti and chalking can encourage serious crimes due to lack of social control. Therefore at community level this issue should be addressed and unacceptable chalking and graffiti should be eliminated through aggressive strategies to improve safety and to eradicate disorder signs. However, this approach seems to have contradiction, as at some places wall chalking is forbidden whereas at some places it is supported. This contradiction can be seen as a positive approach though, because cultural representation or beautification is allowed and on the other hand inappropriate advertisement and political slogans are forbidden. We can say that permission of expression through graffiti is permitted under certain conditions. Well this raises questions also, that some narratives are permitted but some are suppressed and have to face legal actions, this actually reflects the power dynamics.

The integration of Crime through Environmental Design (CPTED) elaborates the layering of graffiti in relation to crime reduction (Shaftoe, 2004). Many European countries encourage altering environment by improving lighting, increased visibility to have well-maintained environment under controlled lawful conditions (Cozens & Love, 2015). The CPTED has shown positive results and culturally meaningful markings to contribute to community's identity. The complications deepen as the community takes control to relay public messages and in some areas walls become the medium for announcements, warnings. Sometimes these messages appear as a tool for safety measures at community level but on the other hands it raises ethical questions as well. As Oli (2019) showed concern that this might lead to uncontrolled vigilantism. Though wall chalking and graffiti is effective medium but it should have certain restrictions to maintain peace and security and it should be properly oversight. Overall images, symbols, chalking etc. on city walls create layered records based on social evolution. Every writing, image and symbol has a story of its own depicting conflicts, harmony, dissatisfaction, protests, desires, and etc. Public spaces are not just areas to consume, but it is a shared and living environment, where people gain identity and shares power to socialize appropriately and in a regularized manner. Many stories and accounts linked with urban life are not found as exhibits in the museums, and on other mediums like social media, electronic and print media, in fact it is found on walls as spontaneous human tracings left on walls as reminders reflecting socio-cultural aspects of the community.

In Karachi, research consistently points to deep-seated social and economic forces—such as poverty, unemployment, limited education, and fast-paced city growth—as the core reasons behind both crime and vulnerability. These conditions create the motive and the opportunity for offenses, while also putting

residents at greater risk of being victimized (Gillani, Rehman & Gill, 2009). Studies in Pakistan confirm that the connection between poverty, joblessness, and crime holds true over the long term, though short-term patterns can shift depending on local circumstances (Khan, 2015). Looking at the city itself, analyses of Karachi and similar areas show that poorly planned spaces, bad lighting, and neglected public areas increase residents' fear and weaken the community's natural ability to monitor and protect itself (Iqbal, 2025). There are proven ways to address these physical flaws. Principles like Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED), which focus on elements like visibility and territorial control, have strong evidence for reducing fear and certain crimes, especially when local communities are actively involved (Cozens, Saville & Hillier, 2005). More recently, public art and murals have emerged as a promising, low-cost strategy. When residents help create these artworks—rather than having them imposed from above—they can strengthen community bonds, bring people into underused spaces, and reduce both the feeling and the reality of disorder (Sakip, 2016; Barton, 2024). The violence in Karachi is deeply rooted in a mix of economic inequality, informal and precarious work, and gaps in governance, which together create pockets of high vulnerability (Hasan, 1999). Neighborhoods marked by deprivation, ethnic divisions, and a lack of formal jobs see higher rates of violent crime, as economic marginalization can push people both into victimhood and into participating in violence (Hamza, 2021). While foundational theories from Jeffery (1971) and Newman (1972) on CPTED and "defensible space" argue that better design can curb crime opportunities, they also warn that physical changes alone are no substitute for tackling underlying social and economic issues. Therefore, for Karachi, the most effective path forward is an integrated one. It must combine socio-economic actions—like creating jobs, improving education, and providing social services—with community-led improvements to the urban environment. This includes practical steps like better lighting and waste management, but also participatory projects like public art and design, which can build social inclusion and informal surveillance (Sharp, Pollock, & Paddison, 2005). Ultimately, lasting safety requires pairing place-making tactics with pro-poor economic and governance reforms to address the true roots of insecurity.

Research Methodology

The research is based on the Critical analysis of crime situation in Karachi and the researchers have focused to study about crime situation and analyses that how through promoting public art and environment can reduce crime rate in Karachi. The researchers have reviewed several studies on public art in the region of Europe where actually the public art has helped to reduce ratio of crime. The researchers have used qualitative approach for analyzing the international and national researches during the period 2010-2022. The techniques used here for conducting research are library research and content analysis, these techniques allows us to analyze and identify research gaps on the basis of empirical evidence and thus providing factual information (Yin, 2018).

Library Research

As stated by George (2008), library research is a kind of research that collects data by learning and understanding data having a close relationship with the problem from theories, books, documents.

Content Analysis

Content analysis is a useful research tool across all types of scientific and business disciplines. It examines the full context of human thoughts and actions or emotional responses by closely examining qualitative data (any form of text or visual image). Analyzable content can be generated through focus group discussions,

interviews, and survey administration. It also could be collected from published materials, historical documents, speeches, news transcripts, and cultural artifacts (photographs, art, etc.). Content analysis results can inform political and government decisions, business strategies, and public education campaigns. They can even help scholars understand communication trends and how people respond to newsworthy events or interact in specific settings. Content analysis is a research method used by sociologists to analyze social life by interpreting words and images from documents, film, art, music, and other cultural products and media. The researchers look at how the words and images are used, and the context in which they are used to draw inferences about the underlying culture. Content analysis can help researchers study fields of sociology that are otherwise difficult to analyze, such as gender issues, business strategy and policy, human resources, and organizational theory.

Conclusion

In the coming years like the current study, this study suggests possible areas for future inquiry. First, there is a need to carry out qualitative research to determine how public art contributes to collective efficacy. Though prior qualitative evaluations of public art has revealed what constitutes successful projects and how relations between neighborhood members are strengthened (Lowe, 2001; Miles & Huberman, 1994). Additionally, previous researches have concentrated on the public art process and its influence on building relationships without examining informal social control. Future researchers should consider the uses of informal social control in relation to crime prevention which stresses that community-oriented works of art act as key deterrents for criminal behaviors (Creswell, 2014). Similarly, artists who engage themselves in public art projects should reflect upon what outcomes they hope their work will achieve and also how they can assess those outcomes. A lot has been asserted concerning public art though it lacks enough reviews so as to justify or question these claims. For meaningful judgments, more attention is needed from people actively working in support of public art creation. Moreover, there would be another possible line of inquiry to explore the extent to what different effects street art and community art movements have? Besides, street art is growing and often done by young individuals. Street art may be perceived as vandalism or valueless even though it may have been initiated by a youth arts program (Daichendt, 2013). Community public art may be more appealing as it suggests that residents are involved in its creation; while the general public tends to think of it as representing their neighborhood or including the beliefs of the people who live there. Finally, some public artwork by outside artists can be placed within a community simply to improve its aesthetic appeal or increase awareness about art without necessarily reflecting any local concerns. For instance, “Sculpture on the Boulevards”, a temporary series of installation art was conducted in Chicago’s Logan, Independence, California, Garfield and Western Boulevards as part of Chicago Cultural Plan (Office of mayor, 2013). This installation had objectives of bringing art and culture to more Chicago neighborhoods, potentially spurring economic growth, attracting tourists and promoting innovation. Frequently, such kinds of artwork do not upset anyone but neither do they make a profound impression on people in spite of what is said in the press releases (Phillips, 1999). In conclusion, future research needs to focus on understanding how different types of public art are perceived and how those perceptions can affect art awareness and neighborhood social behaviors. Lastly, beyond identifying and describing public artwork, future research should evaluate the reliability of constructed scales through knowing the viewpoint of members of the community about their perception as well as knowledge concerning public artwork in their societies. Different perceptions, meanings and values are depicted from public. Furthermore, residents of community may find that a public art work is historically important or aesthetically good but not significant to them personally. In any case, understanding what residents think qualitatively about art would be useful for determining whether public art can represent artistic expression and social critique, as well as affect social behaviors in communities. Public art is far more comprehensive and it requires direct engagement of people who have directly experienced behaviours in community as it is triggered by the emotions, expressions, and social behaviours (Bishop, 2012). The

experiences gained through firsthand knowledge plays a pivotal role in bridging the gap between social life and practical realities based on aesthetic theory lived experiences and community viewpoint.

This study further amplifies connection between public art driven by community and building strong bonding of informal social monitoring, especially where public art is commonly practiced. The results have clearly demonstrated that public art is not just an aesthetic addition in the community, but it builds social bonding, nurtures sense of shared responsibility and it can also help in curtailing violence and intolerance in the society. There is a dire need to conduct more research in this domain to have insight of its importance. Basically it is a tool for positive social change, because it transforms the society not only aesthetically, but also socially, morally, culturally. Though it is a decorative aspect but it creates a productive social aura.

Figure 1: A Pakistani family looks at art work on a wall on a commercial street in the southern port city of Karachi.

Figure 1:

A team of artists and volunteers in Karachi are transforming the city's walls with vibrant, hopeful murals. In a place often marked by violence and chaos, they're using paint to restore a sense of joy and civic pride. There's a well-known Urdu saying, "*Deewaron ke bhi kaan hotay hain*" (Walls also have ears). But here, these walls do more than listen—they speak. And in Karachi, they speak loudly, layered with messages that overlap and interrupt each other. The city's surfaces tell their own stories, from advertisements promising solutions for *mardaana kamzori* (male weakness) to bold political slogans. Walls have long been symbols of division—keeping people out—or of safety, offering protection. Yet these same surfaces are also claimed by the *awaam*, the public, to express views on politics, faith, identity, and culture. They become galleries for art and billboards for commerce. All these forms of wall-writing fall under the broad category of graffiti. Merriam-Webster calls it "unauthorized writing or drawing on a public surface," while Cambridge describes it as "words or drawings, especially humorous, rude, or political, on walls, doors, etc., in public places." At the heart of both definitions is the idea of *publicness*—a private message doesn't quite become graffiti until it enters the shared space of the city, where everyone can see it, respond to it, and sometimes, paint right over it.

For years, the walls of Karachi have told stories. They've never been quiet—just like the city itself. Covered in vibrant art, political slogans, commercial ads, and urgent handwritten messages, these surfaces are in a constant, lively competition for the attention of passersby. We've always been fascinated by this visual noise. What are these walls actually saying? And why has this practice of "wall chalking"—a raw, local form of graffiti—persisted for so long? In 2019, we set out to listen. Our research focused on this specific, grassroots form of communication, which is deeply tied to Karachi's social, political, and economic currents. To understand it, we walked through six different neighborhoods—from the historic grounds around Quaid-i-Azam's Mazaar to the bustling streets of Saddar, and on to Liaquatabad, Orangi Town, Malir, and Shah Faisal Colony. We looked closely, documented, and began to sort the messages we found into different categories, asking not just what was being said, but why it was being said there.

What we discovered were stories hidden in plain sight. Here's a glimpse of what the walls told us.

Figure 2: People looking at the murals painted during the 'Walls of Peace' campaign in the city | Courtesy: I am Karachi

Figure 3: *Abdullah Ahmed Khan with his calligraphic graffiti in Karachi*

Figure 2: & Figure 3: Graffiti is writings or drawings made on a wall or any large scale surface within public view. Graffiti is a broad category art form, which ranges from simple words to elaborated wall paintings. In recent times, graffiti is a major form of expression of cultural & political concerns like racism and income inequality. Over the last few years Pakistan's art industry has expanded its horizons by adapting to innovative and contemporary forms/styles of art trending in the global art community. Young creative minds unaffected by social barriers as well as driven to think out-of-the-box have added much-needed life to the local art scene; one of them is Sanki King, a pioneer of graffiti, calligraphy, sticker art and sneaker art.

Abdullah Ahmed Khan as a kid was very good in drawing & painting" and is known as Sanki King, he at the age of 11 was introduced to the Hip Hop culture at and then came across graffiti art and instantly decided to explore it. Over the next couple of years he became obsessed with it (graffiti) and continued experimenting/exploring the platform. He started playing Counter-Strike in 2003 and at the age of 13 years became an expert player in a short span of time. His fellow gamers started calling him 'Sanki' a word from Urdu language which generally means someone who is 'crazy'. Later on he started doing graffiti as he felt more relatable to it and picked the same name for his recognition, and few years passed by he found out that Sanki actually means a 'deep thinker', which is true reflection of his personality now. He added if we focus on wall graffiti with deep thoughts to give something productive to our society then it will absorb the true

essence of it in their souls. It can be a convenient and effective platform for changing mindsets and transforming the society into a more humane form.

In Karachi, the troubling reality of crime and vulnerability is deeply rooted in the city's fabric. It grows from the stark gaps between rich and poor, often overlooked neighborhoods, and systems of governance that struggle to keep up. Research and experience show us that thoughtful changes to physical spaces—like better lighting, open design, and meaningful public art—can help. These aren't just cosmetic fixes; they foster connection, a sense of ownership and natural watchfulness among residents, making neighborhoods feel safer and more welcoming. But these local efforts can only do so much on their own. To create lasting change, they must be paired with action on the larger issues that fuel insecurity: widespread poverty, a lack of stable jobs, and the exclusion of marginalized communities. The path forward for Karachi, then, is one of connection. It means weaving together smart urban design, community-driven art projects, reliable public services, and economic policies that lift people out of poverty. True safety isn't just about reducing crime—it's about healing the deeper social and economic fractures that allow it to persist. By tackling both the symptoms and the root causes, Karachi can transform its most at-risk areas into places of greater opportunity, inclusion, and peace.

Recommendations

The safe city and safe neighbourhood concept is linked with better and proper lights and police patrolling at different timings to keep everything in order. Normally we do not consider power of the community as priority aspect and if we keep in mind the cultural colours of the community at the time of wall graffiti, we can execute a true picture of the community. Beautification of city through graffiti also impacts mindset and develops civic pride and ownership. This change begins with basic changes in the process and initiatives should be taken from bottom up growth cultivated from ideas and innovative concepts. People living in such communities get along with each other easily and a sense of belonging develops. City planning by incorporating graphic ideas creates strong bonding between residents and they share history Garnet (2017), culture, norms and values and even their issues (Hudson-Smith, Dodge & Doyle, 1998; National Institute of Urban Infrastructure Planning, 2019).

- Public art projects should be guided by a coherent strategy rather than passion alone. Establish clear objectives, expected outcomes, and criteria for selecting initiatives.
- Evaluate existing public art in the area to determine what is working and what needs improvement. This includes visual audits, site visits, and documentation of current installations.
- Create structured channels—surveys, focus groups, community forums—to gather meaningful input from people who live and work in the neighborhood. Their day-to-day knowledge is essential.
- Combine residents' perspectives with empirical indicators such as foot traffic patterns, participation rates, and local crime statistics to guide decision-making.
- Allocate funding and resources toward projects that demonstrate the strongest positive social, cultural, or safety impact based on data and community feedback.
- Continuously track the outcomes of public art initiatives to identify what improves community well-being and what needs adjustment. Use findings to refine future strategies.

- Encourage collaboration among artists, local organizations, government bodies, and community groups to increase support, legitimacy, and sustainability of public art projects.
- Focus on initiatives that not only beautify the environment but also contribute to rebuilding community trust, promoting shared ownership of space, and enhancing neighborhood safety.

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